

NOTES

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Methyl Phenyl Sulphide by *N*-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one in Buffer Medium†

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SEVERAL studies have been reported on the kinetics of oxidation of organic sulphur compounds¹⁻⁶. A survey of literature reveals that kinetics of the oxidation of aryl methyl sulphides by *N*-chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one (NCP) have not been reported. Howard and Levitt⁷ reported that the sequence of the reaction taking place in the oxidation of sulphides must be sulphide→sulphoxide→sulphone. They found that the sulphide→sulphoxide step is very fast. Kinetics and mechanism of the oxidation of sulphide and sulphoxides with oxidants, like peracids, peroxides, chloramine-T, iodine *etc.* in a variety of solvent systems have been reported⁸⁻¹⁰. In this note we present the results of the kinetics of oxidation of methyl phenyl sulphide by NCP which shows first order each in substrate as well as in oxidant.

Experimental

N-Chloro-3-methyl-2,6-diphenylpiperidin-4-one was prepared and purified as described earlier¹¹. Methyl phenyl sulphide¹² was prepared and purified by distillation under reduced pressure. Ethanol free from carbonyl compounds was prepared by refluxing ethanol, silver nitrate and potassium hydroxide. After refluxing, ethanol was distilled through tufton column. Double-distilled water was used throughout the experiments. Other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. pH of the medium was measured using I.T.L. pH meter.

The kinetic studies were carried out in 75% (v/v) ethanol-water by taking the substrate and the oxidant in the ratio 3 : 1. The reaction was followed by estimating the unreacted NCP by the iodometric procedure. The kinetics were generally followed up to 75% completion of the reaction. The pH of the medium was buffered by 0.05 M potassium hydrogen-phthalate.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by

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Fig. 1. Plot of $\log k$ vs $\log [H^+]$.

allowing an excess of NCP to react with the substrate and the unreacted NCP was estimated after the completion of the reaction. The stoichiometry of the reaction is 1 : 1.

The reaction mixture was analysed by tlc and developed by benzene-ethyl acetate mixture (4 : 1, v/v). The reaction mixture was extracted with chloroform from an actual kinetic run after about 75% completion of the reaction. The reaction mixture gave two spots (made visible by exposure to iodine) of R_f values 0.36 and 0.95. They correspond to those of the authentic samples of methyl phenyl sulphoxide ($R_f=0.36$) and methyl phenyl sulphide ($R_f=0.95$), respectively. The reaction mixture does not give any spot corresponding to the sulphone which has an R_f value of 0.75.

Results and Discussion

Effect of varying [substrate] and [oxidant]: The reaction was studied at varying [oxidant] and [substrate], keeping [KHP] and temperature constant (Table 1). The results showed a first order dependence each with respect to the oxidant and the substrate.

Effect of varying ionic strength: The increase of ionic strength ($NaNO_3$) from 0.025 to 0.125 M increased the rate constant from 1.33×10^{-1} to $2.67 \times 10^{-1} \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, showing the participation of charged particles in the rate determining step. In some cases of oxidation reactions¹¹ involving N-halo compounds, the rate is increased considerably in the presence of chloride ion due to the formation of free molecular chlorine. In order to confirm

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF VARYING [SUBSTRATE] AND [OXIDANT] ON REACTION RATE

[KHP] = 5.0×10^{-3} M
Solvent = 75% aq. ethanol
Temp. = $20 \pm 0.1^\circ$

[Substrate] $\times 10^4$ M	[Oxidant] $\times 10^3$ M	k_2 $\times 10^4$ dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹
1.048	1.039	1.09
1.501	1.039	1.11
2.096	1.039	1.07
2.503	1.039	1.07
3.144	1.039	1.06
2.503	0.841	1.08
2.503	1.121	1.09
2.503	1.401	1.08
2.503	1.681	1.16
2.503	1.961	1.14

this, in this case also the reaction was carried out in presence of varying concentration of chloride ion keeping the ionic strength constant. But there is no appreciable change in the rate.

Effect of varying dielectric constant of medium : The reaction was also carried out in five different ethanol-water mixture containing 60, 65, 70, 75 and 80% ethanol and the rate constant were 6.52×10^{-1} , 3.53×10^{-1} , 1.86×10^{-1} , 1.08×10^{-1} and 0.62×10^{-1} dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, respectively. The increase in the rate constant with increase in the dielectric constant of the medium may probably be due to the ion-dipole interaction of the reactants.

Effect of temperature : The reaction was carried out at four different temperatures 15, 20, 25 and 30° using [substrate] = 2.503×10^{-3} M, [oxidant] = 1.039×10^{-3} M and [KHP] = 5×10^{-3} M. The values second order rate constant calculated were 8.28×10^{-2} , 1.07×10^{-1} , 1.37×10^{-1} and 1.79×10^{-1} dm³ mol⁻¹ s⁻¹, respectively. The activation parameters were calculated using linear least-square procedure and it was found that the energy of activation is 37.22 kJ mol⁻¹ with a correlation coefficient of 0.999 (S.D.=0.005) and the entropy of activation 145.4 JK⁻¹ mol⁻¹ with a correlation coefficient of 0.992 (S.D.=0.019).

Effect of varying pH : At constant concentration of substrate and oxidant, and temperature, the reaction was carried out at four pH values. The rate constant was found to decrease as the pH increased. A plot of log k_2 vs log [H⁺] gives a straight line with unit slope showing that the order with respect to [H⁺] ion is one.

Mechanism : The oxidant in acid medium exists in equilibrium with its protonated form which is found to be the effective oxidising species. In our case also the protonated NCP oxidises the methyl phenyl sulphide to methyl phenyl sulfoxide. The mechanism of the oxidation (Scheme 1) has been proposed on the basis of the observed results. The step (2) is the rate determining step which has been proposed on the basis of the first order dependence of the reaction rate each with respect to oxidant and also the substrate.

$$\text{Rate} = k [\text{NCP-H}^+] [\text{PhSMe}]$$

$$\text{where, } [\text{NCP-H}^+] = K [\text{NCP}][\text{H}^+]$$

$$\text{Rate} = K k [\text{NCP}][\text{H}^+][\text{PhSMe}]$$

$$-\frac{d(\text{Oxidant})}{dt} = k_2(\text{obs}) [\text{NCP}][\text{PhSMe}][\text{H}^+]$$

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Limiting Equivalent Conductance of some Higher Valence Electrolytes

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LITERATURE survey^{1,2} shows that not much has been done on the limiting equivalent conductance of higher valence electrolytes. Since we are interested in the diffusional studies of electrolytes of lanthanide and actinide series, we thought it worthwhile to determine the limiting ionic conductance of cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate since their values are to be used in the determination of diffusion coefficient.

A.R. grade cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate were used and the impurities were not more than 0.001%. The solutions of these electrolytes in the concentration range 10^{-4} – 10^{-8} M were prepared in conductivity water with conductance 10^{-6} Ω^{-1} . The measurements were made with the help of a conductivity bridge Model 31 (Yellow Spring Instrument Co., U.S.A.) which can measure conductance as low as $0.1 \mu\Omega^{-1}$. The cell constant was found to be 1.23 with $0.2 N$ KCl. The resistance of the connecting wires was also taken into consideration. The observed conductance of $Ce(NO_3)_3$ at 35° and of $Th(NO_3)_4$ at 45° are presented in Table 1. The plots were made between the equivalent conductance

(Λ_0) and square root of concentration ($\sqrt{C}$) in order to determine the limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) at infinite dilution for both the electrolytes and are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. The values of Λ_0 for cerium nitrate and thorium nitrate were obtained by extrapolation method and are given in Table 2 along with the limiting ionic conductance of Ce^{III} and Th^{IV} .

Fig. 1. Plot of Λ_0 vs. $\sqrt{C}$ for $Ce(NO_3)_3$ at 35°

Fig. 2. Plot of Λ_0 vs. $\sqrt{C}$ for $Th(NO_3)_4$ at 45°

TABLE 1—CONDUCTANCE AND EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCE OF CERIUM NITRATE AND THORIUM NITRATE

Cono. $\times 10^4$ mol dm ³	Thorium nitrate, 45°		Cerium nitrate, 35°	
	Conductance $\times 10^{-3}$ Ω^{-1}	Equivalent conductance Ω^{-1} cm ²	Conductance $\times 10^{-3}$ Ω^{-1}	Equivalent conductance Ω^{-1} cm ²
1	2.20	676.5	0.75	307.5
2	3.40	522.7	1.40	287.0
3	4.70	481.7	2.00	278.8
4	6.00	461.2	2.62	268.5
5	7.00	430.5	3.20	262.5
6	8.10	415.1	3.75	256.2
7	9.00	395.4	4.30	251.9
8	9.90	380.5	4.80	246.0
9	10.10	345.1	5.28	240.5
10	11.00	338.2	5.60	229.6

Cell constant = 1.23.

TABLE 2—LIMITING AND EQUIVALENT IONIC CONDUCTANCE AT INFINITE DILUTION OF SOME HIGHER VALENCE ELECTROLYTES

System	Temp. $^\circ$	Λ_0	λ_0^+	λ_0^-
$LaCl_3^a$	25	145.9	69.56	76.34
$Ce(NO_3)_3$	35	335	249.52	85.48 ^b
$Th(NO_3)_4$	45	665	565.90	99.10

^a G. F. A. Kortum and J. O. M. Bockris, "Textbook of Electrochemistry", Elsevier, New York, 1951.

^b Ref. 2. ^c M. L. Sood, G. Kaur and S. L. Chopra, *Acta Ciencia Indica*, **1979**, 279.